

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Definition: The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.

Dissemination activity name	What? Type of dissemination activity	Who? Target audience (Choose one or more items)	Why? (Max 200 characters)	Status
CUMULUS BUDAPEST 2024	Conferences	Research communities, Industry, business partners, Innovators	Participation in conference including working groups and networking events discussing project results and proposed advances on sustainable design with world-wide research and design institutions	Delivered
CIMODE 2023	Conferences	Research communities, Industry, business partners, National authorities, Innovators, Regional authorities, Civil society	The Fashion Alive project presented a roundtable at CIMODE 2023, an international fashion and design congress held in México from October 4-6, to discuss Fashion Alive developments, and results.	Delivered

COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	Outcome	Status
Newsletters	released periodically following the project calendar, in order to disseminate blog post and contents created on the website, as well as to communicate and encourage the audience to download and use the materials created by the project (portfolios, best practise guides, fashion and runway films)	Innovators	SOCIAL_MEDIA	11 newsletters sent, 1119 subscribers, 18,7% open rate	DELIVERED
Instagram Content	Instagram was used to engage the target groups through regular, visually appealing posts, stories, videos and reels about project activities, events, developments and concepts.	Innovators	SOCIAL_MEDIA	11284 followers, 161 posts created	DELIVERED
Facebook Posts	Facebook was used to engage the target groups through regular, visually appealing posts, stories, videos and reels about project activities, events, developments and concepts.	Innovators	SOCIAL_MEDIA	110 posts created, 996 followers, 2300 page reach, 9900 video reach	DELIVERED

Media publications	<p>The Fashion Alive project mission, events and results were published on the following media outlets: https://www.madridcapitaldemoda.com/evento/fashion-alive-2023/ https://edicionessibila.com/fashion-alive-la-moda-sostenible-que-todos-deseamos-llega-a-madrid-de-la-mano-de-creamodite/ https://ateneodemadrid.com/evento/mesas-redondas-sobre-metodo-zero-waste-fashion-alive-2023-y-sostenibilidad/ https://www.cope.es/programas/solo-copees/cope-cool/noticias/contouring-maquillaje-mate-brillo-con-lewis-amarante-maquillador-las-estrellas-cope-cool-20230530_2736990 https://www.neo2.com/creamodite-o-como-hacer-la-moda-mas-sostenible/</p> <p>https://globalfashionexport.net/gfe-news/fashion-alive-ateriza-en-madrid/ https://edicionessibila.com/fashion-alive-el-proyecto-de-moda-sostenible-realiza-su-performace-presentando-sus-disenos-en-el-ateneo-de-madrid/ https://www.elmundofinanciero.com/noticia/109757/lifestyle-y-moda/fashion-alive-la-moda-%20sostenible-que-todos-deseamos-llega-a-madrid.html https://www.rainews.it/tgr/campania/video/2023/07/fashion-alive-progetto-vanvitelli-511cc1e8-d17e-4b54-8a78-a307183d7c05.html https://www.google.com/search?q=fashion+alive+unicampania&amp;rlz=1C5CHFA_enIT979IT979&mp;mq=fashion+aliv e+unicampania&amp;gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIGCAEQRRg9MgYIAhBFGD0yBggDEEUYPdIBCDM0NTIqMGo0qAlAsAIA&amp;sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8#fpstate=ive&vld=cid:abb48b01,vid:xdCRO6tQmrQ,st:0</p>	Civil society	MEDIA_ARTICLE	10 publications	DELIVERED
Project website	Used to centralize project information regarding its mission, partners and goals, as well as dynamic content promoting the events and project results, through blog posts and a resources page specifically devoted for easy access to project documents.	Innovators	WEBSITE	2519 visitors, 6 pages created, 30 blog posts created.	DELIVERED

YouTube Content	YouTube was used to engage the target groups through runway and masterclass videos as well as the project fashion film	Innovators	SOCIAL_MEDIA	17 videos uploaded	DELIVERED
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Communication: Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

** We would advise to give clear guidance of what we expect. It would be very specific Key performance indicators similar to what is suggested by DG COMM for our corporate communication <https://myintracomm.ec.europa.eu/corp/comm/Evaluation/SiteAssets/Pages/Do-You-Need-Methodological-Guidance/Communication%20Network%20indicators%20.pdf>

FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO THIRD PARTIES

Sub-Calls

Call reference	Call budget	Budget awarded	Call publication date	Call closure date	URL to F&T portal	Call status	Number of received proposals	Number of awarded proposals
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Awarded Beneficiaries

Call reference	PIC	Legal name	Organisation type	Country	Funding awarded(€)	Funding paid(€)	Comment
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EVENTS AND TRAININGS

Events and trainings (including workshops, conferences, etc.)									
Event No	Participant name	Description					Attendees		
		Name	Type	Area	Location	Duration (days)	Male	Female	Total
1	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA CAMPANIA LUIGI VANVITELLI	Fashion Alive Aversa Roundtables	Masterclass and roundtables	Cultural Heritage and sustainable fashion method and main outcomes, project mission and activities dissemination	Aversa , Italy	1	25	40	65
2	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA CAMPANIA LUIGI VANVITELLI	Fashion Alive Aversa Runway Performance	Performance Fashion show	Cultural heritage and sustainable fashion focused on corredo collection promotion via avant garde performance runway shows including digital engagement strategies (videomapping)	Aversa , Italy	1	200	300	570
3	UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO	Fashion Alive Guimaraes Roundtables	Masterclass and Roundtables	Upcycling and sustainable fashion, sustainable fashion innovations and developments in Portugal, project mission and activities dissemination	Guimaraes , Portugal	1	7	11	18
4	UNIVERSIDADE DO MINHO	Fashion Alive Guimaraes Runway Performance	Performance Fashion Show	Upcycling collection promotion via avant garde performance runway shows including digital engagement strategies (LED wall and ephemeral architecture)	Guimaraes , Portugal	1	150	150	350
5	CREAMODITE ASOCIACION PARA LA CONSTITUCION Y REESTRUCTURACION DE EMPRESAS DE MODA DISENO Y TECNOLOGIA	Fashion Alive Madrid Roundtables	Masterclass and Roundtables	Zero Waste Fashion, sustainable fashion developments in Spain, project mission and activities dissemination	Madrid , Spain	1	15	35	50
6	CREAMODITE ASOCIACION PARA LA CONSTITUCION Y REESTRUCTURACION DE EMPRESAS DE MODA DISENO Y TECNOLOGIA	Fashion Alive Madrid Runway Performance	Performance fashion show	Zero Waste Fashion collection promotion via avant garde performance runway shows including digital engagement strategies (light show)	Madrid , Spain	1	100	200	350
7	CREAMODITE ASOCIACION PARA LA CONSTITUCION Y REESTRUCTURACION DE EMPRESAS DE MODA DISENO Y TECNOLOGIA	Sustainable Design Store guided tour	Sustainable design stores guided tour in Madrid	Display, debate and learnings on sustainable fashion arts & design store trends	Madrid , Spain	1	2	5	7